

THE DESCRIPTION OF FRIENDSHIP IN THE DIDACTIC WORKS CREATED IN MOVARUNNAHR AND KHURASAN IN THE LATE 12TH AND EARLY 14TH CENTURIES

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Annotation: *This article presents the views of Farididdin Attar, Burhaniddin Rabguzi, Najmiddin Kubro, Nosiriddin Tusi, Muslihiddin Sadiy, Jalaliddin Rumi, Khusrav Dehlavi on friendship in didactic works created in Movarunnahr and Khurasan in the late 12th and early 14th centuries and its importance in the formation of friendly relations between individuals nowadays.*

Key words: *friend (sincerity), friendship, loyalty, brotherhood, perfection, happiness.*

Friendship has a great place in the spiritual heritage of our ancestors. Especially in the late twelfth and early fourteenth centuries in Movarunnahr and Khurasan, in didactic works by Farididdin Attar, Burhaniddin Rabguzi, Najmiddin Kubro, Nosiriddin Tusi, Muslihiddin Sadi, Jalaliddin Rumi, and Khusrav Dehlavi notions of friendship, choosing a friend and loyalty to friendship were expressed profoundly. If we pay attention to the **descriptions of friendship** described in the works, we can see the struggle of interests and content. The spiritual content of a relationship with a friend is a healthy friendship. It is a bond of healthy friendship, deep devotion and closeness, in which two people can express their uniqueness without fear. The combination of these two allows for the development of an emotional space and emotional aspects that evoke more than just unity. In this regard, Rabguzi's "Qisasi Rabguzi" says about the essence of a friend: "Before doing anything, one should consult a good friend and then do it [1; 174]." Regarding friendship, Najmiddin Kubro said, "I have seen that the most unique blessing is honesty and heroism, and the worst misfortune is hypocritical friends. I have understood that the best friend is science." [263]

Farididdin Attar's scientific legacy also reflects the multifaceted nature of friendship. Attar noted: "Be a friend with smart and intelligent people, escape from stupid and arrogant ones" [4; 130]. Attar says that after establishing friendly relationship: "Don't complain about your friendship to anyone. [4; 220] and

emphasizes about the vices of friendship without thinking only about having benefits which you can gain befriending [4; 390]. In particular, it is impossible to make friends with people who are harmful and self-interested, and a healthy friendship can only come from a person who is a colleague, like-minded and devoted people.

Nosiriddin Tusi in "Akhlaqi Nosiri" expresses the unique role of loyalty in friendship. According to him, "since man is social by nature, his complete happiness is combined with the happiness of loyal people (friends) and the happiness of his co-workers [2; 183] ». The work emphasizes that one's fullness is related to the perfection of others, that one can never reach individual perfection, and that "a perfect and happy person is one who finds many loyal partners, engages them in things that are good for him, and cannot fulfill their happiness." May he be proud of their existence and enjoy them all his life [2; 184]. The philosopher states: "There can be no true friend." [2; 184]. Continuing his thinking on the characteristics of choosing a friend and how to keep a friend, the scholar argues that in order to take advantage of a friend's loyalty, one must study his or her past, his or her childhood, and his or her relationship with loved ones. He noted: "It is said that brotherhood is to do good in return for goodness, praising friendship, gratitude, openness, and condemning ingratitude, ungratefulness, and greed." [2; 185]

The scholar believes that the main reason for friendship to become enmity is arrogance and vanity, and for maintaining friendship friends should share their interests in song, music, dance, poetry, anecdote, merriment, humor and joy.

Tusi says that a person who passes the test of friendship should be considered the most loyal, the most virtuous and such friend should not be missed. He explains that when there are many friends, there is a great demand for friendship, and when one is done, he can ignore the other, and as a result, one is saddened. [2; 185] The thinker should not be mistaken for a friend's small faults in the face of a great deal of devotion, for he says that the perfect man will be left without a friend, and that he will suffer in solitude. He does not neglect any relationship of friendship, and warns his friends and comrades not to deprive him of his prophecies, not to withdraw, and, if possible, not to thank them, if he achieves one of the great tasks. He said, "If one of his friends feels unbelief or coldness, he should not slap him in the face, show him a lot of kindness, and see him a lot. If arrogance, pride, selfishness, inflexibility, resentment, and so on, show itself to be cold, the bonds of friendship will be broken and loyalty will be hampered. It is necessary to take measures to clarify this issue, which is caused by unbelief, and to say

everything openly, sincerely, and without hiding anything. There are many great blessings in truth." [2; 186]

The scholar emphasizes the need to prevent conflicts between friends, to observe the conditions of friendship and to use the virtues of friendship, so that they do not become hostile, and he said that "friendship and deception do not fit together ... In fact, friendship is created for brotherhood and accurate relations." [2; 186]

In Sadiy's view, friendship is also explained as the main notion. He gave various definitions to the word in his masterpiece "Gulistan" and noted that: "It is better to knock on a friend's house than to knock on an enemy's door," and added: "Because the king's friendship is in doubt, and the boy's kindness changes overnight [7; 122]". Regarding the terms of friendship in "Gulistan", he continued saying that: "Don't tell every secret to your friend. It is not surprising that one day he will become your enemy, do not do any harm to your enemy, and one day he may become your friend. Don't tell your best friend the secret you want to hide, because every friend has his friend and the very friend in its place can have his own friend. [7; 127]". Through this idea, the scholar urges people not to divulge every secret to a friend in order to maintain a solid foundation in friendship, but at the same time to be vigilant.

In his view, Rumi describes friendship through loyalty and betrayal. For example, in the "Masnavi", betrayal of a friend is described as one of the evil vices [6;10]:

The human eye is just a piece of the skin,
All you have to do is open your eyes and see your friend.
If you can't see, it's better to be blind,

If friendship is not eternal, be far away of it. [6; 56], - he says. In "Masnavi", Rumi's friendship can be sometimes hostile [6; 239], and he advised when a friend became a stranger, do not long, avoid him, do not talk or converse [6; 429]. Rumi also expressed his view on unfaithful friendship: when the day comes, your friends will ignore you, turn away from you, it means that they stop friendship and will be the enemy [6; 551]. If a snake bites, it can be dangerous for your life, but a vice friend will burn you in the fire [6; 587]. When you are healthy, all your friends are friends, and when you are sick, your friend is only God [6; 605], - he says.

Khusraw Dehlavi's views show a special emphasis on friendship. He states that a sincere relationship with a friend is the first condition for goodness, and if you have made a promise of friendship, keep it and build a firm friendship room. What is the use of friendship if it is not strong, because the oil-free lamp does not

burn [3; 128], - he says. At the end of this idea, a great thinker compares the friendship to a light bulb which lights the surrounding with its bright lights.

In conclusion, it can be said that in the the didactic works of Farididdin Attar, Burhaniddin Rabguzi, Najmiddin Kubro, Nosiriddin Tusi, Muslihiddin Sadiy, Jaloliddin Rumi, Khusrav Dehlavi, which were created in Movarunnahr and Khurasan in the late 12th and early 14th centuries, conditions and qualities of friendship were described skillfully. The main categories of friendship which were mentioned in the works of great thinkers are: healthy friendship, deep devotion and closeness, advice, honesty, heroism, a noble man, a man of integrity, patience, a person who is like-minded and in the interests of the people, loyal, virtuous, benevolent, scholar, colleague, loyal, helpful, kind, grateful, open-handed, smiling, kind, secretive. The content of these categories can be used to form, develop and improve friendships among students in the classroom and in the extracurricular educational process.

REFERENCES:

1. Rabg‘uziy, Nosiriddin. Burhoniddin. Qissasi Rabg‘uziy. - T.: Yoshlar nashriyoti uyi, 2018. - 174 b.
2. Tusi Xacə Nəsirəddin. Əxlaqi-Nasiri. - Bakı, «Lider Nəşriyyat», 2005. - 140 s.
3. Деҳлавий, Амир Хусрав. Ёр васли. - Т.: O‘zbekiston, 2011.- 128 б.
4. Нишопурий, Шайх Фаридиддин Аттор Достонлар. - Т.: «Tamaddun», 2012. - 130 б.
5. Норова, М.Ф. Сайфиддин Бохарзий. - Б.: "Sadriiddin Salim Vuxoriy" Durdoni n., - 56 б.
6. Румий Жалолиддин. Маснавийи маънавий. - Т.: «MERIYUS» ХНМК. 2010. - 56 б.
7. Саъдий. Гулистон. Бўстон. - Т.: Ғафур Ғулум номидаги н.-м. ижодий уйи, 2013. - 122 б.
8. Ҳикоят ва ривоятлар / Убайд Зоконий, Муҳаммад Авфий, Фахриддин Али Сафийб, Абул Фароғ; [Тўпловчи ва тарж. Кибриё Қаҳҳорова]. - Т.: Адабиёт ва санъат нашриёти, 1983. - 240 б.
9. Ҳикоят ва ривоятлар. - Т.: Адабиёт ва санъат нашриёти, 1983. - 240 б.
10. Valeriyevna, I. G. (2022, February). THE VIEWS OF ORIENTAL THINKERS ON SCIENCE AND ENLIGHTENMET AS THE THE CRITERIA OF

THE CONTEMPORARY DEVELOPMENT. In *International Conference on Multidimensional Research and Innovative Technological Analyses* (pp. 173-176).

11. Izbullayeva, G. (2021). NOSIRIDDIN TUSIYNING “AXLOQI NOSIRIY” ASARIDA YOSH DAVRLAR PEDAGOGIKASI VA PSIXOLOGIYASI. *Buxoro davlat universitetining Pedagogika instituti jurnali*, 1(1).

12. Izbullayeva, G. (2020). Mahmud Shabustariyning “Gulshani roz” asari so ‘fiylik ta’limotida muhim manba. *Uzbekistan: Language and Culture*, 4(4).

13. Valerievna, I. G. (2014). PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF JALOLIDDIN RUMIY AND BAHOUDDIN NAKSHBANDIY’S IDEAS. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 2(2).

14. Valerievna, I. G. (2014). PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF JALOLIDDIN RUMIY AND BAHOUDDIN NAKSHBANDIY’S IDEAS. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 2(2).